

Phenylmercury(II) Compounds-II. Some Novel Three-Coordinate Phenylmercury(II) Complexes with Triazene-1-Oxides

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Triazene-1-oxides (TH) react with phenylmercuric acetate to form phenylmercury(II) complexes of the general formula $[C_6H_5.Hg(T)]$. All these complexes are monomeric in freezing benzene. Their structures have been deduced from elemental analyses, conductance, molecular weight and infrared spectra. These complexes have three-coordinate Hg(II) with the ligands functioning as monobasic chelating bidentate ligands.

COORDINATION complexes of triazene-1-oxides with several transition metal ions have been studied by many workers¹⁻⁶. We report in this paper a series of phenylmercury(II) complexes with triazene-1-oxides (I) which are shown to have three-coordinate Hg(II).

Experimental

Materials: Ligands were synthesised by following published procedures¹. Phenylmercuric acetate was prepared according to the procedure given in the literature⁷.

Synthesis of phenylmercury(II) compounds: 0.002 mole of phenylmercuric acetate was dissolved in hot ethanol (~25 ml) and filtered into an ethanolic solution (~15 ml) of 0.002 mole of the ligand. The mixture was refluxed for 15 min and cooled to room temperature. Yellow needle-shaped crystals separated out which were collected on a filter and recrystallised from ethanol.

Similar procedure was adopted for the synthesis of the complexes of the ligands: 3-*p*-tolyl, 1-phenyl triazene-1-oxide.

For the complexes of 3-*p*-chlorophenyl, 1-methyl triazene-1-oxide, 3-*p*-tolyl-1-methyl triazene-1-oxide and 1, 3-diphenyl-triazene-1-oxide the refluxed solution had to be concentrated to a small volume (~10 ml). The complex of 3-*p*-nitrophenyl 1-phenyl-triazene-1-oxide separated out readily and was recrystallised from acetone.

Elemental analyses and physical measurements: Carbon and hydrogen analyses were performed by M/s. Alfred Bernhardt Micro-analytische Laboratorium, West Germany. Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas method and mercury was determined by following our procedure⁸ (Table I). Conductance was measured with a Philips PR 9500 Bridge. IR spectra were run at C. D. R. I., Lucknow. Molecular weights were determined by cryoscopic method using benzene. Characterisation data of phenylmercury(II) complexes of triazene-1-oxides and their molecular weights in benzene appear in Table I.

Results and Discussion

All these complexes are crystalline, highly soluble in chloroform and acetone and moderately soluble in benzene, ethanol and methanol. They have very low molar conductance value ($0.1 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$) which indicates that the complexes are nonelectrolytes. These complexes are monomeric in freezing benzene (Table I).

IR spectra: The expected ir bands for $\nu_{(N-H)}$ ($3150-3200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), $\nu_{(N=N-N)}$ [sym triazene] ($1510-1460 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and $\nu_{(N \rightarrow O)}$ ($1310-1295 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) have all been found in the ir spectra of the triazene-1-oxide ligands⁹⁻¹⁴.

The N $\rightarrow$ O stretching bands of all the pure triazene-1-oxides appear in the region $\sim 1295-1310 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and get shifted to lower frequency in the region $\sim 1230-1245 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in their phenylmercury(II) complexes which suggests that oxygen atom is coordinated to phenylmercury(II). This very sharp band ($\sim 1230-1245 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) also covers a few weak bands in this region. This band is therefore assigned to the combination of C-C (phenyl in-plane) and coordinated N $\rightarrow$ O band.

The strong N-H stretching bands of all the pure triazene-1-oxides completely disappear in their

TABLE I—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF PHENYLMERCURY(II) COMPLEXES OF TRIAZENE-1-OXIDES

Complex	TH		Colour	m.p. °C (dec.)	%Hg	%N	%C	%H	M.W.
	R	Ar							
[C ₆ H ₅ .Hg(T)]	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(p)	Greenish yellow	159-60	38.47 (88.14)	7.92 (8.00)	41.12 (41.19)	2.64 (2.67)	549 (529)
[C ₆ H ₅ .Hg(T)]	OH ₂	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(p)	Colourless	169-70	43.67 (43.38)	9.28 (9.01)	33.67 (33.80)	2.55 (2.60)	452 (461)
[C ₆ H ₅ .Hg(T)]	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ OH ₂ (p)	Yellow	151	40.13 (39.76)	8.44 (8.35)	45.22 (45.32)	3.34 (3.38)	503 (508)
[C ₆ H ₅ .Hg(T)]	OH ₂	C ₆ H ₄ OH ₂ (p)	Colourless	128-29	45.52 (45.85)	9.49 (9.52)	37.98 (38.10)	3.36 (3.40)	445 (441)
[C ₆ H ₅ .Hg(T)]	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (p)	Yellow	195	37.91 (37.45)	10.62 (10.49)	40.84 (40.46)	2.65 (2.62)	528 (534)
[C ₆ H ₅ .Hg(T)]	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	Golden yellow	132-33	41.31 (40.90)	8.72 (8.59)	44.07 (44.18)	3.10 (3.07)	486 (489)

Figures in the parentheses indicate calculated values. The compounds are all non-electrolytes in acetone.

phenylmercury(II) complexes, which is a strong pointer that -N^s nitrogen of the ligand (I) is also coordinated to phenylmercury(II). The $\nu_{(N=N-N)}$ bands are shifted to lower frequencies due to the change in the environment of the triazene which also supports the proposed coordination through a triazene nitrogen.

Strong bands at 725-735 cm⁻¹ and 438-455 cm⁻¹ in these phenylmercury(II) complexes are attributed to Hg-C and Hg-O stretches¹⁵. A new band at 510-525 cm⁻¹ in all these complexes is assigned to ν_{Hg-N} mode¹⁶, which is absent both in the pure ligands and in phenylmercuric acetate.

In view of these observations we wish to suggest structure (II) for the phenylmercury(II) complexes of triazene-1-oxide where Hg(II) is involved in planar three-coordination. A very limited number of three-coordinate Hg(II) complexes have so far been reported in the literature^{15,17}.

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